

Civil society- stakeholder-policy dialogue

MATS Deliverable 6.4

Funded by
the European Union

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Summary

Deliverable 6.4 aimed to facilitate a dialogue between civil society, stakeholders, and policy-makers on the linkages between agricultural trade, markets, investments, environmental sustainability and human rights and wellbeing. While the focus of this deliverable lies on two high-level policy dialogues of which one was held in Europe and another one in Africa, the broader goal is connecting with and strengthening existing networks and platforms.

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Author: Jonathan Matthysen (Oxfam-Solidariteit)

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Contributing Beneficiaries: Co-lead: SEATINI; Support: all MATs partners

¹ R = Report, P = Prototype, D = Demonstrator, O = Other

² PU = Public, CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Introduction

Broader framework: the enhanced engagement strategy

The activities carried out under deliverable 6.4 are integral part of the broader [Enhanced Engagement Strategy \(deliverable 6.2\)](#) of the MATS consortium. Before elaborating on the two high-level policy dialogues (one in Europe, and one in Africa) organised under deliverable 6.4, it is thus worthwhile to frame these activities within our wider strategy.

Target audience

Within our enhanced engagement strategy, the target audience of our two high-level policy dialogues mainly concerns the previously defined Group I, which consists of policymakers, civil society organizations (CSOs), farmer organizations and private sector representatives that are actively involved in promoting and implementing sustainable agriculture trade at local, regional, national, EU and international levels.

Within both high-level policy dialogues, we have aimed to bring together Group I around the processes, and later findings, of the MATS project. To this end, target group II (academics and the scientific community) as well as target group III (farmers in this case) were involved in both high-level policy dialogues.

Since group I may have more leverage than others in transforming trade regimes given their unique position close to or within decision-making centres, both our high-level policy dialogues were designed taking into account the specific needs of this group. On the one hand, this group is difficult to access given their (often) elite position (especially policy makers). On the other hand, the success of this deliverable required deeper and longer interaction between the groups described above, beyond for example a two-hour webinar.

Content design

Firstly, the [Information Needs Assessment \(Deliverable 6.1\)](#) indicated that most of our stakeholders were most interested in Food systems transformation (65% of respondents) and Agri-food trade (55% of

respondents). These two categories remain broad which informed our decision to keep our high-level policy dialogues thematically broad, as opposed to technical niche topics being discussed. Such an approach allowed our high-level policy dialogues to capture a wide interest.

Secondly, our Enhanced Engagement Strategy specifically states that the (interim) results of Work Packages 1 to 5 would feed into the high-level policy dialogues in Africa and Europe. Besides that, we have also aimed to achieve the inverse. That is, to ensure the high-level policy dialogues serve as inspiration for the work carried out under the aforementioned Work Packages. Taking into account the progress of the different work packages and the results of the Information Needs Assessment we have made room in both high-level policy dialogues for this two-way fertilization to happen.

Objectives

In light of the above, the overall objective of the high-level policy dialogues was thus to create a space in which target group I could interact with our project's topic in the framework of facilitated sessions.

For this to be successful the four following sub-objectives were set:

- Objective 1: Create room to have direct engagement with policy makers (from executive and legislative bodies) and experts who hold key roles in shaping trade (for example from certification organisations).
- Objective 2: Aim for cross-fertilization with the work of our target audience on the one hand and the work of the MATS consortium on the other hand. The aim is not necessarily to instigate direct policy changes (for which such format is not suitable) but to inspire the participants, work on thought-leadership of the MATS consortium and do agenda-setting in policy settings.
- Objective 3: Set up collaborations with actors in order to extend our reach and be able to access spaces otherwise closed off to our consortium.
- Objective 4: To have equal representation of women and men in the speakers we bring together, taking into account the commitments made in the Grant Agreement.

In the subsequent parts, we give an overview both high-level policy dialogues explaining how they were designed in light of our objectives.

High-level policy dialogue 1- in Africa

Basic information

- Title: "*Policy dialogues: key insights in agricultural trade*"
- Location:
 - Day 1: Moshi-Cooperative University, Sokoine Road, Moshi, Tanzania
 - Day 2: Kibo Palace hotel, Riadha Street, Moshi, Tanzania
- Date: 23rd of October until the 24th of October 2023
- Participants: 35 in total including policymakers, civil society organizations, farmers' organisations, government representatives and academics

Programme

Content

The full programme is attached in Annex I.

The first high-level policy dialogue opened with speeches from the Executive Directors of the organising parties SEATINI (Ms. Jane Seruwagi Nalunga) and Oxfam-Solidariteit/Oxfam-Wereldwinkels (currently Oxfam België/Belgique) (Ms. Eva Smets). The opening speech introduced the four topics that would set the framework for the rest of the policy dialogue: power, prices, certification and women's rights in agri-food trade.

These four topics were chosen because they are key determinants in the outcomes of specific trade relations. Indeed, trade acts as a catalyst for prosperity in some cases, while in other cases it reinforces existing power relationships and inequality.

- [On power] Trade has transformed economies but has been the subject of change too. Since the beginning of the 19th century trade has grown exponentially at a scale never seen before. Currently, 80% of global value chains can be linked to transnational corporations and about a quarter of total global production is being exported. However, this

growth came at a cost. The (dis)advantages of international and intra-national trade have been distributed unequally as trade was instrumentalized by the powerful.

- [On prices] Following differences in power, the profits of trade are often captured by multinationals and their shareholders, especially at the expense of small enterprises, women entrepreneurs, and rural communities. For that reason, it will be worthwhile for us to take a look at how value is distributed among supply chains. The main factor in this equation is of course pricing. What could we consider as fair prices, and what not?
- [On certification] When talking about trade we cannot forget about the civil society movements that strive towards more justice and sustainable in trade. Since decades, the Fair Trade movement has been a major player in this area. The Fair Trade movement shares a vision of a world in which justice, equity and sustainable development are at the heart of trade structures and practices so that everyone, through their work, can maintain a decent and dignified livelihood and develop their full human potential. One of the many tools the movement use is Fairtrade certification.
- [On women's rights] Trade impacts women, men, and children differently, depending on the cultural, socio-economic and political background in which they operate. While women make up 43 percent of the global agricultural labour force, they are often confined to supporting roles, while men are able to capture more of the value created by exporting agricultural goods. Increasing trade volumes without taking a look at the gendered economics of trade, might thus reinforce existing gender inequalities.

After the opening speech we had two blocks (one on the 23rd of October, the other the next day) which were designed in a similar fashion.

Part 1. Each block opened with two keynote speeches by prominent decision-makers, each setting the scene for one of the four topics, based on their experiences and challenges they encounter. Each such keynote speech took 30 minutes followed by a Question & Answer of 20 minutes. Creating a first space to create a shared understanding and dialogue between speaker and

audience (objective 1). We ended each keynote speech by asking the speaker for one key question (s)he wants to explore deeper in the part 2.

Part 2. After the keynote speeches we continued our dialogue by setting up workshops in the form of hackathons with the aim of deepening our shared understanding and informing each other's work (objective 2).

A hackathon is an event wherein teams focus 'to solve' problems of predefined cases in a limited amount of time. A hackathon is a portmanteau of 'hacking' (or solving) and 'marathon'.

The speakers thus presented the group with four questions in total (one each) at the end of their keynote speech for the participants to solve in parallel groups.

The four questions presented to the participants were the following:

- [On power] How to navigate big power imbalances that shapes global, regional and national legal and poli
- [On prices] What do we change now to ensure Food System transformation by 2030, taking into account food prices?
- [On women's rights] How can stakeholders/businesses/trades ensure responsible and sustainable trade through compliance to certification standards?
- [On certification] How can women be supported to engage in higher value agriculture trade?

For the purpose of these hackathons, the organisers have developed a new method called the Goal-Problem-Solution (or GPS)-method. Its goal is to help workshop participants to navigate and find solutions to so-called "*wicked problems*". These are problems with many interdependent factors making them seem impossible to solve at first sight.

A methodological note on the GPS-method is attached in annex II.

By letting our guest speakers choose the question the participants would 'solve', we ensured that the discussions were of relevance to them and the discussions would inform their decision-making. By inviting the speakers to participate in the hackathons themselves, we aimed to ensure direct interaction (objective 1). With the participation of the different Work Package

leads, we ensured that information from the deliverables (incl. the case studies being developed at that time) were included in the conversation (objective 2). The GPS-method was designed so that it would give a first idea of how high-level pathways could be drawn out for the problems at hand, although time was insufficient to reach this stage.

Speakers

The introduction was done by

- Jane Seruwagi Nalunga (Executive Director, SEATINI)
- Eva Smets (Executive Director, Oxfam België/Belgique)

The four keynote speakers invited to the event where:

- Hon. Odongo George Stephen (Member of East African Legislative Assembly and Chairperson of the EALA Uganda Chapter), who discussed power in agricultural trade,
- Hon. Francoise Uwumukiza (Member of East African Legislative Assembly, Chairperson of the Committee on Agriculture, Tourism and Natural Resources), who discussed prices in agricultural trade,
- Ms. Lina Asiimwe (Eastern African Sub-Regional Support Initiative for the Advancement of Women, EASSI, Gender and Economic Justice Program Manager), who discussed women's rights and their role in agricultural trade, and
- Mr. Isaac Tongola (Executive Director of Fairtrade Africa), who discussed the role of (Fairtrade) certification in agricultural trade.

Through this list, we ensured a gender-balanced podium for our audience (objective 4).

Collaborations

For the first high-level policy dialogue, we have worked together with our MATS partner SEATINI to design the dialogue and establish contacts with African policymakers. We have also collaborated with Moshi Cooperative University to ensure access to the Tanzanian academic world. Moshi Cooperative University also kindly provided the meeting space for the first day

of the dialogue. The MATS coordinator University of Helsinki supported with operations before, during and after the event. Without these collaborations, we would not have been able to establish the high-level policy dialogue in the format it was set up (objective 3).

Promotion and dissemination

For the promotion and dissemination of this event, we have prepared a media package for our MATS partners to share with their networks. The package contained the following:

- Draft e-mail to invite partners
- Digital flyer to share with the e-mail (see annex I)
- A lay-outed programme containing a registration link (see annex I)
- Visuals for social media (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook), introducing our speakers and a call-to-action to register (see annex III)
- Draft social media posts

On the event, we foresaw the following elements.

- A banner for the event
- We invited local media to cover the event (ITV Moshi and Daily News)
- We took photos of the event (available [here](#) for invited people, send e-mail to Jonathan.matthysen@oxfam.org for access).
- Live tweeting during the event

High-level policy dialogue 2 – In Europe

Basic information

- Title: *"Towards sustainable and fair agricultural trade - A future vision for the EU as a trusted partner in the global agriculture supply chains"*
- Location: European Economic and Social Committee, Rue Van Maerlant 2, Brussels, Belgium
- Date: 5th of March 2024
- Participants: 158 registrations in total including policymakers, civil society organizations, farmers' organisations, and academics. Online 51 people participated from 18 different countries. Offline, 72 people participated based on the attendance sheet, although due to logistical issues during the intermission, we were not able to capture everyone's signature.

Programme

Content

The full programme is attached in Annex IV.

The second high-level policy dialogue was opened by the organisers representative from MATS (Mr. Bodo Steiner) and TradeHub (Ms. Marianne Kettunen). They introduced the audience to both consortia and their work and opened the event.

The dialogue was organised in one day but consisted of two parts which mirrored each other. Both parts consisted of two panels (four in total). The first and third panel were more focused on micro-level considerations of the impact of trade (policy) on (smallholder) farmers (i.e. social sustainability). The second and fourth panel were more focused on macro-level considerations of the impact of trade (policy) on the climate and the environment in more general (i.e. environmental sustainability).

The two parts mirrored each other thus in topic but were designed differently to attract different audiences.

Part 1. For the first part, our main target audience was more specialised policymakers, experts from CSOs and academics. In that sense, the panels were more technical with the aim to attract the wider expert community around agri-food trade. Nevertheless, the broad scope of the impact of trade (policies) was kept through the two panels broad themes, which to a degree overlapped since social and environmental sustainability cannot be seen apart.

Each panel was opened by a high-level representative from the European Commission to set the scene. After that, we entered into a discussion with the representative of the European Commission and panellists from academia and civil society organisations.

The two panels focused respectively on the following questions.

- Panel 1: Making trade deliver sustainability benefits to smallholders, what do we know about good practice? How do we scale up good practice?
- Panel 2: How sustainable is global agriculture trade? What are the trending discussions and emerging issues linked to environmental and social sustainability, at global level and from different regional perspectives? What is the kind of agriculture trade we need and want moving forward, including in the changing climate?

Part 2. For the second part, our main target audience was the more public side of policymaking and interest-representation with European Parliamentarians, farmer(s') representatives, civil society organisations and representatives from youth organisations taking part. In that sense, the panels -called policy-practice exchange or PxP- were aimed at having a more political and accessible discussions of the same topics at hand (objective 2).

By the time the second high-level policy dialogue was held, our Work Packages had advanced and so we were able to feed these discussions with findings and policy recommendations from our case studies. Both panels were thus opened by a MATS or TradeHub representative setting the scene by sharing some of our results.

The third panel was opened by a representative from MATS who highlighted (a) the importance of adopting smallholder sensitive policies, (b) the need to have policy support with the aim of reaching living incomes, and (c) the interconnectedness between all facets or pillars of sustainability – social, economic, and environmental. These three topics were illustrated with specific findings from a selection of case studies.

The fourth panel was opened by a representative from our co-organiser TradeHub who highlighted (a) the linkages between trade agreements and the climate mentioning the need for a shared but differentiated responsibility to climate change, and (b) the need to have policy coherence when it comes to the trade regime, highlighting examples from case studies on energy policy and the Common Agricultural Policy.

After each scene-setting, the debate was opened between the Member of European Parliament, farmers and youth representatives and civil society organizations. Each debate was moderated by a journalist from EUObserver.

Audiences could ask questions to all panellists throughout the day via the Q&A function of the online platform. These were diffused by the moderators to the panellists (objective 1). We also shared with the participants an invitation to the Work Package 5 workshop the day after (objective 2) (see annex VI).

Speakers

The introduction was done by

- Bodo Steiner (MATS Coordinator & Professor, Food Economics & Business Management, University of Helsinki)
- Mariane Kettunen (Coordinator TradeHub)

Panel I Towards more sustainable and fairer deals for smallholders

- Leonard Mizzi (Head of Unit, Sustainable Agri-Food systems and Fisheries, DG INTPA, European Commission)
- John Comer (EESC rep. Group III, president ICMSA)
- Louise Nakagawa (Researcher, Imaflora Brasil)
- Jonas Ngouhou Poufoun (Visiting scientist, International Institute of Tropical agriculture, IITA)

- Herry Purnomo (Senior Scientist and Indonesia Deputy Country Director CIFOR-ICRAF)

Panel II: Trade we have vs. trade we want - making agriculture trade just, nature-positive and supportive of climate action

- Flavio Coturni (Head of Unit, Agriculture, Food and Sanitary and Phytosanitary Matters, DG TRADE, European Commission)
- Christophe Payot (Director Trade Policy, FPS Foreign Affairs, Belgium)
- Beatriz Fernandez (Associate Programme Management Officer, UNEP Trade and Environment Hub)
- Geneviève Pons (Director-General and Vice President, Europe Jacques Delors)
- Matthew Langdon (Trade Programme Associate European Climate Foundation, ECF)

Policy and Practice Exchange I (panel III): smallholder farmers & social sustainability

- Helmut Sholz (Member of European Parliament, INTA committee)
- Marceline Budza (President and founder, Rebuild Women's Hope)
- Morgan Ody (General coordinator, La Via Campesina)
- Simon Guérin-Sanz (representative of Young Fair Trade Advocates, YFTA)
- Sylvia Kay (Representative MATS, Transnational Institute)

Policy and Practice Exchange II (panel IV): trade, climate and the environment

- Saskia Bricmont (Member of European Parliament, INTA committee)
- Saker El Nour (RESEAU TANMO)
- Adélaïde Charlier (representative of Fridays for Future)
- Lisen Runsten (UNEP WCMC)
- Mathilde Dupré (Institut Veblen)

Through this list, we ensured a gender-balanced podium for our audience (objective 4).

Collaborations

For the second high-level policy dialogue, we worked together with [Trade, Development & The Environment Hub](#) (in short: TradeHub) who co-organised the event with us. They were essential in increasing our outreach and coordinating such a big event. Besides TradeHub, we have also established a partnership with the European Economic and Social Committee (EESC) who provided us access to speakers and provided the meeting venue. We have also discussed with the EESC to bring this event under the umbrella of the EU Civil Society Week. The MATS coordinator University of Helsinki supported with operations before, during and after the event. Through these collaborations we have been able to extend our reach and therefore the success of this deliverable (objective 3).

Promotion and dissemination

For the promotion and dissemination of this event, we have prepared a media package for our MATS partners to share with their networks. The package contained the following:

- Draft e-mail to invite partners
- Digital flyer to share with the e-mail (see annex IV)
- A lay-outed programme containing a registration link (see annex IV)
- Visuals for social media (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook) including banners and a call-to-action to register (see annex V)
- Draft social media posts

On the event, we foresaw the following elements.

- We have engaged with Politico and EUObserver to cover the event. EU-Observer moderated our afternoon debates.
- We took photos of the event (available [here](#) for invited people, send e-mail to Jonathan.matthysen@oxfam.org for access).
- Live tweeting during the event

For interested parties that were not able to attend the event, we have foreseen publicly accessible recordings.

- [Panel I Towards more sustainable and fairer deals for smallholders](#)

- [Panel II: Trade we have vs. trade we want - making agriculture trade just, nature-positive and supportive of climate action](#)
- [Policy and Practice Exchange I \(panel III\): smallholder farmers & social sustainability](#)
- [Policy and Practice Exchange II \(panel IV\): trade, climate and the environment](#)

Annex I Programme & Flyer high-level policy dialogue I

Making Agricultural Trade Sustainable

Programme
High-level policy dialogue

Monday 23th of October afternoon, Moshi Cooperative University

EAT	13:00	14:00	15:00	16:00	17:00	18:00
	Hybrid	Hybrid	Hybrid	In person	In person	In person
	Welcome from Executive Directors SENTINI & OXFAM (13:30-13:50)	Expert speaker 1 - power in agricultural trade: Hon. Odongo George Stephen (13:50-14:40)	Expert speaker 2 - the role of (un)fair prices: Hon. Franciose Ukwumukiza (14:40-15:30)	Introduction to concept of hackaton	Hackaton Group 1: power in agricultural trade (16:00-17:00) Hackaton Group 2: the role of (un)fair prices (16:00-17:00)	Presentation of results of both groups

Tuesday 24th of October morning, Kibo Palace Hotel

EAT	09:00	10:00	11:00	12:00
	Hybrid	Hybrid	In person	In person
	Expert speaker 3 - Fair-trade certification: Mr. Isaac Tongola (09:00-09:50)	Expert speaker 4 - agricultural trade and women's rights: Ms. Sheila Kawamara (09:50-10:40)	Hackaton Group 3: Fairtrade (10:55-11:40) Hackaton Group 4: women's rights	Presentation of results of both groups

The output of the hackatons will be transformed into a derivative product (for example a mind map, think piece or policy brief, depending on the knowledge generated) and shared with the expert speaker afterwards. It will also serve as inspiration to our endeavours in WP 5.

● Hybrid
● In person

We decided in favour of in-person hackatons as the concept requires dynamic interaction between the participants.

For participating online to the expert speaking sessions, please register [here](#).

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Making Agricultural Trade Sustainable

Policy dialogues

Key insights in agricultural trade

Power in Agricultural Trade

Hon. Odongo George Stephen
Chairperson, EALA Uganda Chapter
Member of East African Legislative Assembly

Monday 23th of October, 13:50 EAT - 14:40 EAT
12:50 CET - 13:40 CET

The role of (un)fair prices

Hon. Francoise Uwumukiza
Chairperson of the Committee on Agriculture,
Tourism and Natural Resources
Member of East African Legislative Assembly

Monday 23th of October, 14:40 EAT - 15:30 EAT
13:40 CET - 14:30 CET

Fairtrade certification in agricultural trade

Mr. Isaac Tongola
Executive Director Fairtrade Africa
Tuesday 24th of October, 09:00 EAT - 09:50 EAT
08:00 CET - 08:50 CET

Agricultural trade and women's rights

Ms. Lina Aslimwe
Gender and Economic Justice Program Manager
EASSI

Tuesday 24th of October, 09:50 EAT - 10:40 EAT
08:50 CET - 09:40 CET

Join digitally

Register [here](#).

Join in person

Moshi, Tanzania

23th of October
[Moshi Cooperative University](#)

24th of October
[Kibo Palace hotel](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000751.

Photo: © Marsano Herrera Jennifer Kateeba, Ugandan farmer, member of the ACPCU cooperative

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Annex II Methodological note GPS-method

Making Agricultural Trade Sustainable

METHODOLOGICAL NOTE

The GPS-method

The methodology used in these hackathons was developed especially for this purpose. The method is dubbed the GPS-method and is aimed at navigating so-called wicked problems, i.e. "problems with many interdependent factors making them seem impossible to solve"¹. GPS stands for Goal-Problem-Solution.

Firstly, participants write down their goal in the middle of a large paper. For the purpose of this hackathon, we used the questions provided to use by the speakers.

In a second step, participants to the hackathon were asked to formulate the barriers that prevent the current system of reaching the goal. This helps out to deepen out the problem at hand and create a shared understanding of the challenges. The problems are written in a concentric circle around the central goal. Arrows can be drawn between problems to illustrate relationships.

In the third step, those around the table are asked to formulate solutions that address as much of the problems as possible. This should lead to solutions that in theory are most effective. These 'big ideas' do not necessarily have to be realistic or attainable in the short run. This stimulates out-of-the-box thinking. The solutions are written in an additional concentric circle around the problems. Here too arrows can be drawn to illustrate relationships.

Your paper after step 1, 2 and 3.

In the final step, the second and third step are reiterated as much as needed for the 'big ideas' to become more realistic and attainable in the short run, i.e. broken down in subtargets. Hence, the identified problems in this step will be a reality check on the solutions of step 3. The identified solutions in this step will be realistic versions of their counterparts in step 3.

Your paper after step 4.

The result is a map which reflects the environment with which policy-makers and decision-makers are confronted with: a sea of problems in which those ideas have to be found that have the potential of addressing them. As all policy makers are constrained in their power and resources, practical ways have to be found to make these ideas attainable in the short run.

If comprehensive enough, the GPS-map can be used to draw out pathways that may inform the direction in which political power is ought to be used. If new problems arise, then new pathways can be drawn out.

Pathways, purposive to your goal.

¹ The Interaction Design Foundation (2023). <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/topics/wicked-problems#:~:text=Wicked%20problems%20are%20problems%20with,approach%20provided%20by%20design%20thinking.>

Annex III Social media materials high-level policy dialogue I

<p>Policy dialogues</p> <h2>Key insights in agricultural trade</h2>	
<p>Power in Agricultural Trade</p> <p>Hon. Odongo George Stephen Chairperson, EALA Uganda Chapter Member of East African Legislative Assembly Monday 23th of October, 13:50 EAT - 14:40 EAT 12:50 CET - 13:40 CET</p> <p>The role of (un)fair prices</p> <p>Hon. Françoise Uwumukiza Chairperson of the Committee on Agriculture, Tourism and Natural Resources Member of East African Legislative Assembly Monday 23th of October, 14:40 EAT - 15:30 EAT 13:40 CET - 14:30 CET</p>	
<p>Register now at https://shorturl.at/glQ48</p>	<p>Register now at https://shorturl.at/glQ48</p>

Register at <https://shorturl.at/glQ48>

Register now!

Policy dialogues

Key insights in agricultural trade

Annex IV Programme & Flyer high-level policy dialogue II

Towards sustainable and fair agricultural trade

 European Economic and Social Committee

 MATS
making agricultural trade sustainable

 TRADE, DEVELOPMENT & THE ENVIRONMENT HUB

The projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000751 (MATS) and UK Research and Innovation's Global Challenges Research Fund (UKRI GCRF) project number ES/500816G/1 (TRADE Hub).

 UK Research and Innovation

Towards sustainable and fair agricultural trade

A future vision for the EU as a trusted partner in the global agriculture supply chains

Welcome words 9:00 am - 9:15 am CET

Panel discussions

Panel I Towards more sustainable and fairer deals for smallholders

9:15 am - 10:45 am CET

Making trade deliver sustainability benefits to smallholders, what do we know about good practice? How do we scale up good practice?

Panel II: Trade we have vs. trade we want - making agriculture trade just, nature-positive and supportive of climate action

11:00 am - 12:30 am CET

How sustainable is global agriculture trade? What is the kind of agriculture trade we need and want moving forward, including in the changing climate?

Policy and Practice Exchanges (PxP)

Policy and Practice Exchange I: smallholder farmers & social sustainability

1:30 pm - 3:00 pm CET

A discussion of policy recommendations of the Make Agricultural Trade Sustainable project and TradeHub with Members of European Parliament, civil society representatives, farmer organizations, and youth movements.

Policy and Practice Exchange II: trade, climate and the environment

3:15 pm - 4:45 pm CET

Closing remarks 4:45 pm - 5:00 pm CET

Photo: © M. Nugle and Andito Wasli/Oxfam.
Konsorsium Timor Adil dan Setara.

Speakers

Panel discussions

Panel I Towards more sustainable and fairer deals for smallholders

9:15 am - 10:45 am CET

Leonard Mizzi
HoU Sustainable Ari-Food systems and Fisheries, DG INTPA, European Commission

John Comer
EESC rep. Group III, president ICMSA

Louise Nakagawa
Researcher, Imaflora (Brasil)

Jonas Ngouhou Poufoun
Visiting scientist, International Institute of Tropical agriculture (IITA)

Herry Purnomo
Senior Scientist and Indonesia Deputy Country Director
CIFOR-ICRAF (Indonesia)

Panel II: Trade we have vs. trade we want - making agriculture trade just, nature-positive and supportive of climate action

11:00 am - 12:30 am CET

Flavio Coturni
HoU, Agriculture, Food and Sanitary and Phytosanitary Matters, DG TRADE, European Commission

Christophe Payot
Director Trade Policy, FPS Foreign Affairs, BE

Beatriz Fernandez
Associate Programme Management Officer, UNEP Trade and Environment Hub

Geneviève Pons
Director-General and Vice President, Europe Jacques Delors

Matthew Langdon
Trade Programme Associate
European Climate Foundation (ECF)

Policy and Practice Exchanges (PxP)

Policy and Practice Exchange I: smallholder farmers & social sustainability

1:30 pm - 3:00 pm CET

Helmut Sholz, MEP (INTA)

Marceline Budza, Rebuild Women's Hope

Morgan Ody, La Via Campesina

Simon Guérin-Sanz, YFTA

Sylvia Kay, TNI

Moderation by Wester van Gaal (EUObserver)

Policy and Practice Exchange II: trade climate and the environment

3:15 pm - 4:45 pm CET

Saskia Bricmont, MEP (INTA)

Saker El Nour, RESEAU TANMO

Adélaïde Charlier, Fridays For Future

Lisen Runsten, UNEP WCMC

Mathilde Dupré, Institut Veblen

Moderation by Wester van Gaal (EUObserver)

Annex V Social media materials high-level policy dialogue II

EESC, MATS and TRADE Hub proudly present

Towards sustainable and fair agricultural trade

Panel discussions & policy-practice dialogues

Register now!

The projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000761 (MATS) and UK Research and Innovation Global Challenge Research Fund (GCRF) project number ES0581601 (TRADE Hub).

Annex VI Flyer workshop Work Package 5

The flyer features a background image of a woman in a white lab coat and safety glasses, looking slightly to the side. The text is overlaid on this image. At the top, there are logos for MATS and Fraunhofer. The main title is in large, bold, white letters. Below it, the subtitle is in a smaller, italicized font. Two paragraphs of text describe the workshop's purpose and format. At the bottom, there is a date and time, a registration instruction, a meeting location, and a note about limited places.

 MATS
making agricultural trade sustainable

 Fraunhofer

Transition Pathways and Policy recommendations workshop

H2020 Project MATS WP5 Workshop

With the 2035+ vision for a sustainable trade future the MATS consortium developed in Tanzania, we are best equipped to start initiating the transition processes. In the WP5 workshop we will integrate “the view from outside” the MATS project and want to include contributions from a broad spectrum of stakeholders.

After briefly looking back at the results from the visioning process, we will start with the interactive part. In a World Café setting we will collect ideas and options for action towards transition, as well as talk about trends and trade-offs and start to discuss starting points for policy recommendations.

Photo: © Mariano Herrera/Oxfam, Tabaruka Rihisah from the Fairtrade ACPCU cooperative

6th of March, 2024
9:00 am - 15:30 pm CET

Places are limited, so register quickly!

Join in person
Register by sending an e-mail to petra.sandker@isi.fraunhofer.de

Meeting room Artemisia
Mundo Madou

Avenue des Arts 7-8
1210 Brussels, Belgium